

SECTION II

THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE INTERNATIONAL LINGUISTIC SPACE

THE ROLE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN TEACHING COMPUTER SYSTEM PROGRAMMING

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Abstract:

This article discusses the features of teaching English and its importance in teaching programmers. A cross-sectional and comparative analysis of the influence of English language proficiency on academic performance in technical areas was carried out. Recommendations on the implementation of developments in education are given.

Key words: analysis, method, research, programming, English

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In the world of computer programming, English seems to be the lingua franca for coding. Regardless of the source programming language, most keywords are still in English. The computer industry really grew out of technologies developed by the Allies, which were mainly used by the Americans and the British.

IT is a global phenomenon and affects many facets of life. Often, the important elements of life that we have come to rely on are directly related to a particular technology. This means that there must be a way to communicate with stakeholders and users of this technology to ensure maximum benefit. When the application of a particular technology is local, communication in order to understand and use it becomes a local problem. It may even be achievable with the help of the local language.

However, there are certain technologies that go beyond one culture, nation or country. There are common needs that affect the entire globe and thus require collective experience, skills and efforts from global communities.

It was also said that most people learn English in order to use existing programming languages, so it continued in the same spirit when creating new ones. Trying to use other languages for coding would prevent effective communication between programmers, most of whom are already used to the standard, i.e. coding in

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English. However, there is a growing movement and support for the development of non-English code.

The information technology industry encompasses many professional disciplines. Knowing or memorizing these words and related vocabulary in English can be a challenge even for native English speakers.

It is noteworthy that if you do not work in this industry, you may not be aware of these interrelated specializations or what kind of English is required. It will be useful to refresh your memory of the most common expressions in order to work well in a new position. As we discussed earlier, there are tasks in your day-to-day responsibilities as a software developer that benefit certain English grammatical structures and vocabulary.

Most of the new codes are actually developed by English-speaking people. But not all program codes are in English. Although most keywords are written in English, comments, user-written variables, classes, and methods are often written in the programmer's native language.

More than a third of programming languages were developed in English-speaking countries. But some of the well-known and commonly used programming languages have been developed in non-English speaking countries, such as Switzerland (PASCAL), Denmark (PHP), Japan (Ruby), Brazil (Lua) and the Netherlands (Python).

Against the background of big data, people gradually realized that information is an important resource. Thus, it has become an inevitable trend towards innovation and improvement of traditional teaching methods. In the era of big data, multimedia teaching methods have also been used in teaching courses. At the same time, the language teaching method as a whole also reflects its unique advantages in teaching and has made some progress. Thus, this article attempts to combine the educational background of big data and multimedia and use their advantages in learning in order to find effective teaching methods that contribute to students' mastery of vocabulary.

The effect of language learning for students in the real environment of the target language is very important. In the lessons, teachers pay attention to the construction of a language environment, for example, language representation. When organizing pre-English classes for students, classroom introduction, introduction to basic reading, classroom activities and discussion, the target language is used to guide students and create a good English-speaking atmosphere for students, and students naturally adapt to the use of logical reasoning in English to think about problems, organize language and deduce language into the atmosphere of learning English while learning programming.

English words are used more often due to the high-tech industry. The advantage of English is that it is spoken by many hundreds of millions of people. A language using non-English keywords probably won't have the necessary demand to support it. English seems to be well adapted for programming. In most native languages, finding short equivalents of keywords can be a difficult task.

The status of the main body of the student, the manifestation of initiative and the positioning of learning needs are respected. Students are performers who actively accumulate knowledge. The teacher respects the students' academic performance in

the classroom and gives them time for reflection and practice, but they will not be bothered by the students' speech defects.

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